
Growing as a Person: From Befriending the Self to Befriending the Other

Keith D'Souza, SJ

St. Xavier's College, Mumbai

Abstract: Growing as a person often entails a long journey from befriending the self to befriending the other. This journey may be depicted in terms of a wide spectrum that consists of numerous states of awareness. One pole of the spectrum is an extreme form of self-absorption, while the other pole is an expansive sense of being other-oriented. There are three broad ranges of awareness on this spectrum: befriending the self, befriending others largely within one's community and befriending others beyond one's community.

Personal growth is an ongoing task and challenge, in order that higher ranges of this spectrum may gradually characterize the general state of one's consciousness. For this to happen, there is need for adequate situational or contextual grounds for growth to thrive, as well as the need for personal discernment, so that higher levels of awareness are experienced at a greater frequency, intensity and duration.

Cite this article as: D'Souza, Keith. (2021) Growing as a Person: From Befriending the Self to Befriending the Other (Version 1.0). Jnanadeepa: Pune Journal of Religious Studies, July 2021(Vol 25/3), 40-57. <http://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.4459888>

Keywords: Personal growth, befriending the self, befriending the other, states of awareness, transpersonal growth, trans-community growth.

Human growth entails a long and often tedious journey involving many elements: discovering oneself, relating with others, living in community and being open to transcendent realities and values. Living a wholesome human life thus entails some form of success in processing intrapersonal, interpersonal, communitarian and transcendent experiences in a salubrious manner.

This article will focus on what it takes to live a wholesome personal life, in the larger context of the human, cosmic and divine world. The main thesis proposed is that an optimal trajectory or hierarchy of states of growth extends from a basic mode of befriending oneself at a lower extreme, towards ultimate human fulfillment in some self-transcendent form of befriending the ‘other,’ at a more refined and wholesome extreme. The operative presupposition is that optimal personal growth needs to factor in community concerns and relationships, as well as the larger cosmic and divine world of meaning and value.

We will first consider a few of the more obvious features – or general conditions or observations – related to the theme of personal growth. We will then identify a few of the more necessary normative principles that govern growth, keeping in mind that personal growth needs to take into account larger realities such as communitarian, global, cosmic and divine dimensions. The main feature of the article then follows, viz., a presentation of ten states of consciousness which delineate this range of possible levels of growth. A brief clarification and explanation of this apparently linear progression of these states of consciousness then follows.

1. Primary Facets of Personal Growth

There are many features and aspects related to the theme of personal growth. Some are more central, while some may

be considered to be more peripheral. I will present some of the more obvious features or characteristics of personal growth, as a necessary background in order to understand more adequately the nature and status of the states of consciousness which represent increasingly more wholesome ways of being human.

1.1. Personal Growth is a Mystery

The journey from being born a human animal towards the realization of the fullness of being human may be best described as a “mystery.” It does not require much observation or research to realize that while some persons make easy leaps and bounds in terms of growth, others find growth to be an extremely slow and even painful process.

While specific professions, programmes and processes oriented towards personal growth seem to abound, growth is not something that can be mechanically or systematically induced. One of the main theses in Gerald May’s insightful book titled, *Simply Sane* (May, 1993), is that professional exercises geared towards engineering personal growth do not typically meet with expected success. This is not for want of good expertise on the part of the diverse professionals employed, but rather because of the nature of the object under consideration and exploration, viz., the human person. The person is more a mystery to be understood wisely, rather than a problem to be examined, explained and experimented with statistically or scientifically.

Those who appear to be delinquent or deviant may often show signs of growth under more salubrious conditions and circumstances, while those who appear to be more integrated and centred may likely have arrived at this point in their personal journeys after long personal and social struggles. This is in keeping with the popular adage that “saints have a past, and sinners have a future.” Even the best human beings are influenced by what some theorists like Jung refer to as “shadow” dimensions of the self. There are aspects to human existence that do not easily fit

into the categorizations that one understandably employs in the human or social sciences.

When growth is forced towards specific objectives, tragic results may be generated, especially in cases of forced socialization or brainwashing. This often happens in social movements which are ultra right in conviction and orientation. Such programmes and processes often result in violent forms of social expression, and often do untold damage to persons who come within their ambit and influence. This is because the human person cannot be reduced to the same status as an object in the natural realm, or a merely passive recipient of programmes of indoctrination.

1.2. Growth is Contextually Influenced

While there is no doubt that personal growth remains a mystery, it is also quite evident that salubrious social contexts undeniably aid the progress of growth, especially during the first few years of human development. Healthy economic, political and cultural factors are very important as supportive conditions for personal growth. On the other hand, social discrimination and marginalization based on gender, race, class, caste, religion, etc., all have a very important part to play in stunting human growth. A girl child growing up in a heavily patriarchal society hostile to female development has much more of a hurdle to face than one growing up in more egalitarian cultural contexts.

Besides culturally discriminatory and oppressive forces, political instability, economic uncertainty, forced migration and war – all of these leading to physical hardship, deprivation and violence – constitute even more severe conditions for human wellbeing to take place. Some human beings have a privileged start – especially a vast majority of those in materially developed nations – so experience better conditions for growth to take place effortlessly and steadily. However, there is no guarantee that those who live in healthier social climes will *ipso facto* experience better growth trajectories.

1.3. Growth Requires Personal Effort

While extraneous circumstances have a lot to contribute towards the growth of individuals, the disposition and effort that the individual invests in his or her own development has perhaps the most part to play in personal growth. At the beginning of the human journey, unlike other animals, the human animal requires a lot of attention merely for physical survival. At later stages of the human journey, this extraneous support needs to be mirrored by an internal support process, involving consistency and tenacity of effort, resilience or the ability to bounce back from adverse situations.

There are numerous examples of individuals who have suffered tremendous social hardships, yet have bounced back in order to make a personal success of their lives as well as to productively contribute to society. Hence, social context is not the sole category which determines a trajectory of growth. Besides social conditions, individual differentiation has a large part to play when it comes to personal growth. Most parents will easily agree that while the social resources placed at the service of their children were very similar, each sibling turned out quite differently from the others. This is the psychological and spiritual challenge to sociological, anthropological and statistical generalizations. This is also in continuity with thesis 1.1. above, viz., that personal growth is a mystery and not something that can be easily mastered or even fully comprehended.

1.4. Growth may be Measured by Different Parameters

The issue of personal growth is a highly contentious one, with different schools abounding in different social or human sciences, each of them proposing competing parameters or criteria by which growth may be measured. Among the more well-known theories of personal development are the psychodynamic theory proposed by Freud and developed by Erik Erikson, and the cognitive-structuralist theory proposed by Jean Piaget and developed by Lawrence Kohlberg. While some theories give more importance

to the experiences of early childhood, others give importance to cognitive capacities, while yet others pay more attention to social adaptability and capacity building, such as the cultivation of emotional and social intelligence.

This divergent approach is mirrored by different cultural estimations with regard to how human beings ought to manifest growth patterns. Some cultures give more importance to conformity with traditional practices, while others value independence and autonomy at an early age of adulthood. Among the former, which stress the communitarian dimension, are tribal or indigeneous societies – and also a growing tendency among right-wing ideologues and activists, which some attribute to a reaction against globalization. Other cultures, which are more influenced by urban and capitalistic lifestyles and attitudes, favour individualism and personal autonomy as more authentic indicators of growth. The former or more traditional focus highlights what the person owes to his or her society, while the latter or more liberal focus highlights what the person achieves or contributes to society, by way of creativity, enterprise and risk.

2. Normative Principles Governing Personal Growth

Determining the criteria governing the issue of personal growth or “human development” is a complex and sometimes contentious process. Among the diverse theoretical schools dealing with personal development, the psychologically influenced ones give importance to personal dimensions of growth, while the sociologically influenced ones give importance to social relatedness and productivity and the spiritually influenced ones give importance to sensitivity towards transcendent and divine reality.

In this exercise we move from the descriptive realm of the ‘is’ to the prescriptive or normative realm of the ‘ought.’ While proposing norms – and later, a hierarchy of states of consciousness based on these norms – for determining personal growth, I have taken into consideration various psychological,

social, moral and spiritual aptitudes requisite for integral and ongoing development.

At the *personal level*, primary among the indicators of growth is integrity, or having and living by strong and upright moral principles and convictions. This requires emotional and spiritual intelligence and depth. Reliability and consistency of character is a strong indicator of integrity. When these principles and convictions are increasingly autonomous and not only dependent on social convention or pressure, the quality of integrity gets even more refined. Besides integrity, an important quality is resilience, or the ability to bounce back from adverse circumstances. Resilience is generally founded upon a core optimistic or positive outlook towards life. Finally, persons of integrity may be relied upon as being responsible for tasks assigned to them. Also, such persons assume responsibility for their actions and their outcomes, and do not easily attribute blame to others or social situations.

At the *interpersonal level*, integrity is manifested in honesty or truthfulness in communication. The principle of the Golden Rule – present in diverse forms in various cultures and religions – is adhered to, with mutuality and justice given a high premium in relationships. Beyond duty and justice, a spirit of sensitivity and compassion, and a concomitant valuation of mercy above justice are further indicators of a heightened quality of interpersonal relationships.

At the *social level*, personal and professional transparency is esteemed, associated with the value of accountability. The desire to contribute productively to society – and to “give back,” especially from a situation of privilege – is also given a high premium. Establishing a social situation that features fraternity and harmony within one’s primary communities and with persons of other communities in general is also valued. The idea of the “common good” takes precedence over the narrow, privatized idea of the “individual good.”

Finally, at the *trans-human and trans-social level*, respect for nature and natural resources is increasingly gaining ground as a moral imperative today. Beyond and beneath this, a sensitivity, receptivity and collaborative disposition towards the presence and working of transcendent and ultimate spiritual realities are also important factors in furthering personal growth.

3. States of Growth

Growing as a person may ideally be depicted in terms of a trajectory that consists of numerous states of awareness. One pole of the trajectory is an extreme form of self-absorption, while the other pole is an expansive sense of being other-oriented. Beyond a deficient or dysfunctional state of existence in which one is not able to even befriend oneself, there are three broad spectrums of awareness on this trajectory: befriending the self, befriending others within one's community (being at home within one's community's horizon of meaning and purpose) and befriending others beyond one's community (being at home with communities and concerns that transcend one's own and one's community's horizon of meaning and purpose).

3.1. Individually Focused Growth: Befriending the Self

Befriending oneself is not as easy as it seems, given the stresses and strains of family and social life. A primal, yet prevalent state of existence that many human beings find difficult to transcend is that of a nagging self-doubt, self-pity and even self-loathing. Beneath these sentiments lies a range of emotions such as fear, shame and unhealthy guilt. In these circumstances, it is difficult to befriend even oneself, leave aside the other. This state of existence may be characterized as *phobic*, as many of the emotions experienced are related to some form of fear or anxiety. Psychoanalytic theorists pay special attention to early childhood experiences – especially related to different forms of fear – to help explain later dispositions and behaviour patterns. However, besides personal wounded memories and lack of opportunities for freedom and flourishing, there may be various oppressive

social situations which cause phobia: economic uncertainty, political strife, cultural marginalization – all of these are factors which do not easily allow people to go beyond this dysfunctional state of consciousness.

The most basic manner of befriending oneself may at first be manifested in *egotistic* or severely self-centred, narcissistic behaviour. This may seem personally and socially dysfunctional, but it is somewhat better than being plagued by powerful negative forces (at the *phobic* level) that leave one psychospiritually scarred and crippled. While narcissism may have its origins in personal life narratives, it may also be caused by strong cultural factors. For example, living in a strong capitalistic milieu naturally gives rise to a spirit of competition for goods and services. In such situations, educational institutions and corporate industries encourage pitting oneself against others in diverse fields of productive enterprises.

The next state beyond the egotistic may be termed the *aesthetic*, in the limited and technical sense in which Kierkegaard uses it as a primal or basic stage of human flourishing. This state of consciousness corresponds to a life driven by the pursuits of varied pleasures. There is a need to get out of one's skin in order to engage with the larger world, even though this engagement may largely be characterized by instrumental relationships. It is important to differentiate this form of aestheticism from a higher form of aesthetic enjoyment, in which the focus is not the self but rather the aesthetic object in itself – or even better, the aesthetic experience, which goes beyond subject-object duality.

Beyond the pursuit of pleasure, perhaps the best state of awareness within the limited spectrum of “befriending the self” is that of *authentic* living, understood as strategically planning and achieving one's personal goals, and thus satisfying one's ambitions in life. Some forms of existentialist thought which advocate authenticity – and in a different light, contemporary corporate culture which encourages personal achievement and success – foster this self-oriented outcome of personal choices

and achievement as a wholesome goal of human existence. While the thought of the early Heidegger may well represent the ideal of authenticity from an existentialist perspective (Heidegger, 1962), the objectivist philosophy of Ayn Rand may best represent the wisdom of living from this type of consciousness at the social, corporate and even ideological level.

When egotism, aesthetic pleasure and personal success are relativized in terms of a more important and wider value or focus, then one's consciousness automatically moves to a higher realm. This may be either furthering the interests of a community or communities with which one is identified, or even beyond, manifesting a concern about the larger human community or the trans-human realm of meaning and value.

3.2. Community-Focused Growth: Befriending the Other as Self

Growing as a person can hardly come to a terminus by merely fulfilling self-oriented goals. The impetus to befriend oneself needs to graduate to a higher level, to include befriending those with whom one shares common interests, a common vision and purpose of life, shared community practices, a collective cultural and religious background, etc. However, while affirming all of these commonalities, there is a movement to befriend the other to a large extent because the other mirrors – or is viewed as an extension of – the self. This type of awareness may then be properly termed, “befriending the other *as self*.”

Within this broad spectrum of “befriending the other as self,” there are at least three types of awareness. The most basic level is an *organic* awareness, in which one recognizes the need for social, legal and institutional order and one's place in such a shared order. Middle order managers, or those who desire to see that everything is in order and that the system runs smoothly are those who especially appreciate such a consciousness. Such a consciousness also features as a default initial state of mind for a majority of tribal or indigenous communities the world over,

in which a collective sense of belonging is valued far above individual attention, pleasure or achievement.

Beyond this basic affirmation of a commonly ordered life is a more refined *moralistic* awareness, where one is convinced of and reifies core moral – and often religious – values associated with law and order. Most culturally and religiously based traditional societies lay great emphasis on the cultivation of such a consciousness. However, there may also be dysfunctional forms of operating from this consciousness, e.g., that which is found among right wing groups, be they religiously bigoted, narrowly nationalistic or culturally chauvinistic.

When one is able to relativize and transcend the narrow observance of the law for its own sake – and for a greater social or moral good – this leads to a more radical understanding of befriending the other. Such a disposition may be termed *empathetic*, as personal compassion prevails over legal, social and moral perfection, and mercy prevails over justice. From such a position, persons are judged to be more important than principles, relationships more important than rules and regulations, and the expression of personal care more important than the mere execution of one's duty.

3.3. Trans-Personal and Trans-Community Focused Growth: Befriending the Other as Other

This interpersonally refined empathetic state of awareness is a threshold towards – and sets the conditions for – an even more evolved state, in which one is able to allow for personal and communitarian differences with one's own horizon of meaning and purpose. It is this level of awareness that may generally be referred to as “befriending the other,” but more properly as “befriending the other *as other*.” This form of awareness too may be broken down into at least three discrete types. An *altruistic* awareness is the most basic, in which one recognizes the value of “alterity” or “otherness.” This entails an admittance that there are persons and communities who live by different values, and

are possessed of a different vision and purpose in life, and that all of these have a unique status and value and ought not be reduced to one's own way of life. Based on this consciousness of alterity, contemporary currents of postmodern critique point towards many glaring instances of discrimination based either on a binary polarization (male-female, white-'coloured', clergy-laity) or a hierarchical system (class, caste). This heightened consciousness is able to recognize and affirm the mutual rights of other communities.

However, a mere admittance or recognition of "otherness" does not automatically entail that one has the inclination or the ability to genuinely empathize with people of other communities. This requires a more proactive *agapeistic* awareness – an extension of the empathetic attitude towards the other as other. Compassion and concern for those of other communities and the cultivation of companionship – etymologically, "breaking bread together" – with the other are constitutive elements of this state of awareness. One of the clearest examples of a person operating from such a consciousness is Mother Theresa, who cared for the lowly and the dispossessed from all religious, cultural and national communities. There are many non-governmental and non-profit organizations whose members also operate from such a consciousness, thus transcending the limited concern exhibited by governmental and corporate agencies – the former operating from national interests, and the latter largely from monetary interests.

Beyond even this benevolent disposition lies perhaps the highest state of awareness that humans may reach in terms of personal development. At this level of being, it is quite likely that the awareness of a self which is separate from any other reality breaks down. In this *mystic* state of awareness, one is suffused with an ecstatic experience that may be characteristic of a wide variety of ultimate values – based on one's fundamental spiritual orientation – such as love, beauty, goodness, wellbeing, existential truth and unity (harmony, interconnectedness). Numerous examples of great mystics from the different religious

traditions abound: Plotinus, John of the Cross, Sankaracharya, Ramakrishna Paramahansa, Aurobindo. However, there are numerous instances in the lives of ordinary human beings which may also feature flashes of this overcoming of duality between the self and the other, and a momentary experience of some form of transcendent reality, which in many cases may be indescribable or even unable to recall with accuracy (Egan, 1989 & Carse 1995).

Beyond these examples of extraordinary and ordinary mystics, are numerous examples of persons who systematically moved beyond individual and community wellbeing, and embraced trans-community or universal wellbeing as their goal, e.g., Buddha, Socrates, Jesus, Gandhi, Mother Theresa. Many such people found themselves living at a heightened state of human consciousness. Unfortunately, some of these – and many others – had to pay with their lives for the novel and radical vision and values they propagated to their contemporaries.

4. The Tenuous Nature of the Different States of Growth

It is tempting to consider these states of consciousness in terms of linear and progressive *stages* of growth. Also, we often assign a “character” to persons who seem to operate from a particular state of consciousness. However, regression to lower states of consciousness is always possible – and likewise, progression to higher states. Even if a person operates from a particular state of consciousness in a regular and sustained manner, it is quite possible that he or she goes through diverse experiences ranging from the phobic to the mystical during the course of a day. This will largely depend on extenuating circumstances and how one decides to respond to these circumstances. Thus, while it may appear to be natural that growth takes place in a linear manner – that is, moving from one state to the next in a steady progression – the extenuating conditions governing human life and corresponding personal responses to them introduce

necessary nuance and ambivalence into an otherwise apparently progressive perception of human growth.

People living in urbanized, capitalistic governed societies may largely be driven to live their lives at a more individualistically focused level, while those who live in rural, traditional or indigenous (tribal) societies which value communal belonging and interconnectedness over individual achievement, will by default live at higher levels of consciousness on the normative scale provided. However, a more integral pathway towards a full human life seems to naturally include all these three types of befriending: befriending oneself, befriending others in one's community and befriending the 'other' beyond oneself and one's community. A person living at higher states of consciousness will not ideally negate or repress previous experiences associated with lower states. Instead, he or she needs to build upon the past by organically synthesizing or integrating past experiences at lower states into subsequent experiences at more refined and wholesome states of consciousness.

Conclusion

Personal growth is an ongoing task and challenge, in order that higher ranges of the spectrum of growth proposed may gradually characterize the state of one's awareness. For this to happen, one needs to ensure that there are adequate external or circumstantial conditions for higher states of awareness to thrive. Besides fostering these situational conditions for growth, however, it is also necessary to discern how to respond to external stimuli – especially in adverse circumstances – in an enlightened manner, so that higher levels of awareness may be experienced at greater frequency, intensity and duration.

The attainment of consciousness at more refined states is both a task and a gift, and one cannot be assured that such a state persists without conscious effort. There is thus need for regular discernment or some form of ongoing awareness exercise, to sustain a higher level of consciousness and wellbeing. Growing

as a person is a lifelong personal project. But it is also a spiritual, moral and social obligation. Because the journey of growth from befriending oneself to befriending the other is not just an exercise in personal or interpersonal growth – it is also a spiritual, moral and social imperative.

Notes

1. Besides professional spiritual directors, counselors, psychologists and psychiatrists, the number of “life coaches”—especially in urban, materially developed contexts—is increasing exponentially, hardly meeting the need and demand of those who are willing to pay exorbitant amounts for the therapeutic mentoring exercises offered by these experts.
2. See also Marcel, 1951:149, where Marcel asserts that, “we must reject the idea of there actually being a legitimate answer, an objectively valid answer, to the question: ‘Who am I?’ . . . [It is] a riddle that, at the human level, simply cannot be solved: it is a question that does not imply, and cannot imply, any plain answer.”
3. This is the wisdom in having growth-oriented remedial programmes in places of incarceration, so that prison inmates may look towards a humane life after serving their term.
4. See Francois O’Kane, *Sacred Chaos: Reflections on God’s Shadow and the Dark Self*. Toronto: Inner City Books, 1994, which is an application of Jung’s understanding of the shadow to human, and even to divine life.
5. Peter Berger and Thomas Luckmann point out to possibilities of brainwashing in the context of the differentiation between primary and secondary socialization. See *The Social Construction of Reality: A Treatise in the Sociology of Knowledge*. London: Penguin, 1966, 149 ff.
6. See Thomas, 1997, for a summary description of various theories dealing with human development, from a secular as well as religious point of view.

7. See D'Souza, 2014: 301-23, for a philosophically-based schema of these ten states of consciousness, and D'Souza, 2015 for a theologically and religiously-based schema of these states.
8. While the emotions of shame, guilt and grief are apparently discrete from that of anxiety or fear, all of these emotions in some way stem from the imagined possibility of losing something valuable: name and status (in the case of shame), integrity (in the case of guilt) and a significant or prized relationship (in the case of grief).
9. According to Françoise O'Kane, in *Sacred Chaos*, 15, "those symptoms and reactions described as characteristic of a narcissistic personality can also be viewed from a different perspective: they are part of an attempt at survival, a way for the individual to confront despair over a life that, for whatever reason, has been dominated by shadow and destruction."
10. Besides the aesthetic or pleasure-oriented stage (exemplified by Don Juan and Faust), the more advanced stages are the ethical (exemplified by Socrates) and the religious (exemplified by Abraham). See Kierkegaard 1992 & 1992a for a description of these three types of stages.
11. See Rand, 1993 for a good overview of her philosophical position advocating individual flourishing.
12. The Pharisees depicted in the Gospels—who considered themselves to be upright or "righteous" (Mk. 7: 1-23; Mt. 15: 1-3)—are a good example of people assiduously living by such a consciousness.
13. The various conflicts over the interpretation of Sabbath laws between Jesus on the one hand and the Scribes and Pharisees on the other (Mk. 2: 1-12, 23-28; Mk. 3: 1-6) are a good example of conflict between one who operates from empathy (Jesus) and one who gives more importance to the adherence of contemporary social and moral codes (the religious leaders who opposed Jesus).
14. One of the main differences between these stages of consciousness and Lawrence Kohlberg's six moral stages of growth—which has been the original framework which I have worked

upon to posit these ten states—is that Kohlberg seemed to have a more rigid cognitive understanding of the nature of these stages, besides not allowing room for regression to take place. For other differences between Kohlberg's six stages and these ten states, see D'Souza 2014

References

- Berger, Peter and Thomas Luckmann. (1966). *The Social Construction of Reality: A Treatise in the Sociology of Knowledge*. London: Penguin.
- Carse, James. (1995). *Breakfast at the Victory: The Mysticism of Ordinary Experience*. NY: Harper One.
- D'Souza, Keith. (2014). "Levels of Existential Development," in D'Souza, Kieth. (ed) (2014). *The Dynamics of Development: Negations and Negotiations*. Bangalore: Asian Trading Corporation.
- D'Souza, Keith. (2015). "Living Faith in a Postmodern World: Principles and Phases of Faith Development" in *The Quality of Adult Faith*, ed. Cleophas Fernandes. Bangalore: NBCLC
- Egan, Harvey. (1989). "The Mysticism of Everyday Life," in *Formative Spirituality Bulletin* (Duquesne), 10/1.
- Francois O'Kane. (1994). *Sacred Chaos: Reflections on God's Shadow and the Dark Self*. Toronto: Inner City Books.
- Heidegger, Martin. (1963). *Being and Time*, trans. John Macquarrie and Edward Robinson. NY: Harper and Row, 1962.
- Kierkegaard, Soren. (1992). *Concluding Unscientific Postscript*, ed. and trans. Howard Hong and Edna Hong. Princeton, NJ: Princeton Univ Press.
- Kierkegaard, Soren. (1992). *Stages Along Life's Way*, trans. Walter Lowrie. NY: Schocken Books.
- Marcel, Gabriel. (1951). *The Mystery of Being*, Vol. 1. Chicago: Charles Regnery Co.
- May, Gerald. (1993). *Simply Sane: The Spirituality of Mental Health*, 2nd ed. NY: Crossroad.
- Rand, Ayn. (1963). *For the New Intellectual*. NY: Penguin.

Thomas, R. Murray. (1997). *Moral Development Theories – Secular and Religious*. Westport, CT: Greenwood Press, 1997.

Dr Keith D'Souza SJ is Rector, St. Xavier's College, Mumbai and President, Association of Christian Philosophers of India (ACPI). He taught Philosophy at St. Pius College, Mumbai and continues to teach philosophy at various institutes. His PhD is on philosophical hermeneutics (Paul Ricoeur and Hans Georg Gadamer). Email: keith@jesuits.net: ORCID: 0000-00020-3967-3013.

Article Received: Nov 4, 2015

Article Approved: Nov 6, 2020

No of Words: 5050

© by the authors. This is an open-access article distributed under the terms and conditions of the Creative Commons Attribution (CC BY) license. (<http://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0/>).

“Today, when the networks and means of human communication have made unprecedented advances, we sense the challenge of finding and sharing a ‘mystique’ of living together, of mingling and encounter, of embracing and supporting one another, of stepping into this flood tide which, while chaotic, can become a genuine experience of fraternity, a caravan of solidarity, a sacred pilgrimage. Greater possibilities for communication thus turn into greater possibilities for encounter and solidarity for everyone. If we were able to take this route, it would be so good, so soothing, so liberating and hope-filled! To go out of ourselves and to join others is healthy for us. To be self-enclosed is to taste the bitter poison of immanence and humanity will be worse for every selfish choice we make.” - Pope Francis